

Mental Health and HIV/AIDS: The Need for an Integrated Response

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ABSTRACT

Context of the study: Impressive biomedical advancements in HIV prevention and treatment have led to aspirational efforts to end the HIV epidemic. However, these efforts will not achieve the desired goals without addressing the significant mental health and substance use problems among people living with HIV (PLWH) and people vulnerable to acquiring HIV. These problems aggravate the many social and economic barriers to accessing adequate and sustained healthcare, and are among the most challenging barriers to achieving the end of the HIV epidemic. Rates of mental health problems are higher among both people vulnerable to acquiring HIV and PLWH, compared with the general population.

Research objective: The objective was to find out how psychosocial influences relating to faster disease progression include life-event stress, sustained depression, denial/avoidance coping, and negative expectancies affect mental health of PLWH. Conversely, protective psychosocial factors like active coping, finding new meaning, and stress management. In studying long survivors of HIV/ AIDS, we found protective effects on health of life involvement, collaborative relationship with health care provider, emotional expression, depression (conversely), and perceived stress (conversely).

Research Methodology: A considerable body of evidence is reviewed in this article. Various articles and research publications relating to mental health of PLWH were taken into consideration. Psychosocial factors play an important role in progression of HIV infection, its morbidity and mortality.

Key findings and practical implications: Despite the significant challenges that mental health presents to HIV prevention and treatment, there are many important and unmet opportunities to integrate mental healthcare with HIV care. Finally, biological factors are also a major determinant of disease progression and include genetics and age of the host, viral strain and virulence, medication and several immune response factors on which psychosocial influences could impact. However, we need to prioritize mental health treatment with appropriate resources to address the current mental health screening and treatment gaps. Integration of mental health screening and care into all HIV testing and treatment settings would not only strengthen HIV prevention and care outcomes, but it would additionally improve global access to mental healthcare.

Keywords: AIDS; Stress; HIV prevention and treatment cascade, integrated care, mental health.

Introduction

Immense advances have been made in HIV prevention and treatment since the discovery of the virus that causes AIDS. In present times, most people newly diagnosed with HIV can live a normal lifespan with steady access and their adherence to a combination antiretroviral therapy (cART). Moreover, in recent years there is great optimism about the potential to end the HIV epidemic – or at least substantially ‘bend the curve’ of the epidemic – with current biological and behavioral tools.

Preexposure prophylaxis (PrEP) is highly effective at protecting individuals from acquiring HIV when taken consistently (Fonner et al, 2016). Furthermore, according to Rodger A et al, people living with HIV (PLWH) who maintain durable viral suppression do not transmit the virus to sexual partners, and in the case of pregnant women, to infants via pregnancy and delivery (Rodger et al, 2016).

According to The Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS) 2025 target, they aim to achieve the 95–95–95 HIV testing, treatment and viral suppression targets within all populations including children and adolescents living with HIV by 2030. Adopted by United Nations Member States in June 2021, alongside ambitious targets for primary prevention and supporting enablers, the 95–95–95 HIV testing, treatment and viral suppression targets aim to close gaps in HIV treatment coverage and outcomes in all sub-populations, age groups and geographic settings (UN General Assembly 2021). UNAIDS goals of ‘95–95–95’ call for 95% of PLWH to be diagnosed, with 95% of them initiating cART, and 95% of people initiating cART to achieve and sustain viral suppression through adherence to the treatment. Given these advances, many jurisdictions are making concerted efforts to turn the tide of the epidemic through PrEP scale-up for individuals vulnerable to acquiring HIV, and improved HIV diagnoses and rapid provision of cART for PLWH. In the UNAIDS report for 2021, they intimated that some localities are moving toward even ultimately ‘getting to zero’ new HIV infections. Although these goals are aspirational, many believe they are achievable with focused resources and concerted efforts.

Nonetheless, these goals cannot not be achieved without addressing the notable mental problems among people vulnerable to acquiring or living with HIV. These mental problems aggravate the many social and economic barriers to accessing adequate and sustained healthcare. Mental problems are among the most significant barriers to achieving the 95–95–95 targets. It is thus worth noting that it will be impossible to significantly approximate an ending of the HIV epidemic without dramatically altering our approach to diagnosing and addressing associated conditions mental health problems among people most vulnerable to HIV not minimizing substance use.

Despite significant advancements in the treatment and management of HIV, individuals living with the virus continue to face substantial mental health challenges. The prevalence of mental health disorders among people with HIV is markedly higher than in the general population, with depression, anxiety, and stress-related disorders being particularly common (Miller & Rockstroh, 2019; Thompson et al., 2021). These conditions not only diminish the quality of life but also interfere with effective HIV management, as they can affect medication adherence and engagement with healthcare services (Santos et al., 2020).

The concept that susceptibility to, and course of, infectious diseases might be influenced by psychosocial factors has a very long history. The historical basis for studying the relationship between psychological stress and the immune response has been noted from centuries of clinical observations of individuals who became sick following stressful situations.

Pathophysiology of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV)

The Centers for Disease Control (CDC) has categorized HIV infection into four different groups based on the presence or absence of disease and clinical or laboratory findings. The four groups are: an acute infection, an asymptomatic infection, persistent generalized lymphadenopathy, and, finally, AIDS. Shortly after exposure to HIV, infected individuals will develop high levels of plasma HIV RNA and mount an HIV-specific immune response. Although viraemic, no measureable antibodies are found at this time. During this early phase, the virus enters and spreads throughout the lymphoid tissues (such as

the lymph nodes, spleen and tonsils), and various organs containing lymphatic tissues (e.g. intestines) or resident macrophage cells (e.g. brain microglia). A persistent viral replication begins, which occurs throughout the course of the disease. Initial viraemia is partially controlled by the immune response to the virus, particularly by CD8 cells, until eventual immune depletion occurs. After the acute phase is over, individuals enter into what may be a prolonged asymptomatic phase (CDC group 2). During this time the infected individual has antibodies to HIV (seroconversion), and is asymptomatic; yet 90% of those infected experience some form of CD4 (helper T) cell decline within 5 years.

Burden of mental disorder

Mental disorders are a mental health condition with high diagnostic importance. These disorders manifest as changes in cognition, emotion and behaviour, and may be accompanied by painful experiences or dysfunction (Vargas et al., 2020). Mental disorders are increasingly recognised as leading causes of disease burden. The Lancet Commission on global mental health and sustainable development emphasised mental health as a fundamental human right and essential to the development of all countries. The Commission called for more investment in mental health services as part of universal health coverage, and better integration of these services into the global response to other health priorities (Patel et al, 2018)

In the general population, mental and substance use disorders are the number one contributors to number of years lived with disability, with greater impact than other communicable, maternal, neonatal, nutritional, and non-communicable diseases, including HIV, and injuries. Excess mortality among persons with mental, neurological, and substance use disorders is evident, with a shortened life span of approximately 15–20 years. The global burden of these disorders rises in late adolescence and peaks in young adulthood, which emulates the global HIV burden.

According to Levchenko, the pathogenic factors of mental disorders are divided into two categories: (1) biological factors, such as inheritance and infection and (2) social and psychological factors, such as stressful life events and personality characteristics. Because the aetiologies and mechanisms of these diseases remain not fully understood, these diseases can be distinguished only by a series of heterogeneous signs and symptoms that often overlap among different diseases (Levchenko et al., 2020).

Mental health receives in general limited research investment and political support in comparison with other non-communicable diseases (NCDs), and the need for a greater investment in mental care and a more equal distribution of funding across African countries has been highlighted (Castelpietra et al, 2020). Further, there is a need for representative population-based studies using defined diagnostic criteria and standardized methods to assess mental disorders among European young people.

Mental health and HIV acquisition

Mental health conditions occur at higher rates among people living with HIV than among people without HIV, in Africa (Geofrey et al, 2023). This Mental health disorders play a critical role in HIV acquisition across populations, increasing the risk of HIV acquisition. Mental health is often neglected in clinical practice, however, despite associations between these conditions and poor health outcomes. One clinic in Nigeria documented that 20% of patients with HIV had a missed diagnosis of depression, for example, which is in keeping with findings from Europe and North America. Most of the literature on psychiatric conditions among people with HIV focuses on depression. In research conducted in sub-Saharan Africa, the prevalence of major depressive disorder ranged from 13% to 24% in mixed groups

of people with HIV on and off therapy. Anxiety, substance use disorders, and post-traumatic stress disorder are also common among people living with HIV and are associated with disability and increased mortality in this population. (Haas et al, 2020)

Various mental health conditions are risk factors for HIV acquisition, and when these conditions coexist, the risks may be aggravated. Mental health conditions can also complicate HIV treatment: depression, for example, is associated with reduced adherence to antiretroviral therapy (ART).

Some populations of people living with HIV may be at particularly high risk for coexisting mental health conditions. Women are more likely than men to have depression during their lifetime, and women with HIV may have higher rates of anxiety and depression than men with HIV. During the peripartum period, ART adherence challenges associated with postpartum depression may affect the risk of vertical transmission (Geofrey et al, 2023).

The association among mental health conditions, poor engagement in HIV treatment, and poor HIV-related outcomes is well documented. In a large meta-analysis, which included more than a dozen studies conducted in Africa, the likelihood of having good (at least 80%) ART adherence was 42% lower among people with depressive symptoms than among those without depressive symptoms.

The need to address coexisting mental health conditions — which can both increase the risk of HIV acquisition and affect HIV treatment outcomes — is acute in Africa, where most of the people living with HIV worldwide reside. Several screening tools are available, some of which have been evaluated in low- and middle-income countries for specific conditions. Further work developing screening and diagnostic tools will be needed, and clinicians will require training in the use of these tools. Stigmatization of mental illness and criminalization of behaviors associated with a high risk of HIV transmission may also make people reluctant to disclose relevant mental health symptoms, even when screening and treatment programs are in place (Geofrey et al, 2023)

People living with HIV are at high risk of mental, nervous system and substance use disorders and mental health disorders can affect general health, adherence to ARV drugs and retention in care. Although chronic HIV care settings provide an opportunity to support and integrate the management of mental health disorders among people living with HIV, this is often overlooked by health systems. Despite effective prevention and treatments for common mental health conditions, including depression and anxiety, and substance use conditions in people living with HIV, which can be implemented in low- and middle-income countries, treatment and care for these conditions, are often not integrated into packages of essential services and care.

Mental health disorder and outcomes along the HIV care surge

There is substantial evidence that impairment in mental health leads to negative health outcomes at each step in the HIV care continuum, starting with being diagnosed with HIV, all the way to achieving viral suppression. Research has shown that lack of HIV diagnosis jeopardizes the health of PLWH by impeding access to the significant health benefits that cART confers. Lack of HIV diagnosis presents a further public health challenge because a substantive proportion of new HIV infections are attributable to persons who are not aware of their HIV status (Remien et al, 2019). As such, mental health disorder that results from major depression, alcohol or other substance use abuse or dependence or significant levels of psychiatric distress (e.g. elevated depressive, anxiety, or PTSD symptoms) can interfere with

regular HIV testing and learning one's HIV status, as well as successfully linking to HIV healthcare, staying in care, initiating cART, and remaining adherent to cART to achieve HIV viral suppression. This can be come risky to the overall health of the PLWH.

Mental disorders can present a substantial barrier to adequate engagement and retention in HIV primary care. Research has established links between the presence of psychiatric illness and poor rates of HIV care linkage and retention. The aspect of the HIV care continuum, which has been most, studied in relationship to mental health, is cART adherence. Research has clearly identified depression as one of the strongest predictors of poor cART medication adherence.

HIV, Depression, and the human immune system

According to studies, there is evidence suggesting a bi-directional relationship between depression and the immune system (Evans et al, 2002). Many of the physical changes caused by depression, such as insomnia or a lack of deep sleep, are thought to weaken your immune system. The immune system is negatively affected by depression in that it causes CD4⁺ to decline. Chronic immune activation and hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis dysregulation, which HIV infection can exacerbate (Norcini et al, 2016), are established factors contributing to developing depression and likely contribute to high rates of depression among PLWH. HIV crosses the blood brain barrier causing immune activation in the brain and the central nervous system. Inflammatory proteins (e.g. C-reactive protein, cytokines) lead to oxidative stress and neuronal injury, specifically, the chronic inflammatory response to HIV infection leads to elevated cytokine levels, including IL-6 and TNF- α , which can trigger a chain reaction involving Tryptophan depletion through the activation of Indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase enzyme (Cans et al, 2020). Tryptophan depletion leads to reduced serotonin levels, increased Kynurenine, and its metabolites, which are neurotoxic and associated with depression, suicide, anxiety, and physical health conditions, such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases and premature death (Siedner et al, 2014). Therefore, it is possible that chronic inflammation and tryptophan depletion contribute to the deleterious effects of depression on physical health outcomes.

The innate branch of the immune system constitutes the primary line of defense against infection, and includes the complement system, Toll-like receptors, and phagocytic cells (Justin et al, 2020). The adaptive branch evolved later and includes B and T lymphocytes, whose immune-receptor and immunoglobulin genes undergo somatic rearrangements to detect new antigens and produce corresponding antibodies. Regulatory lymphocytes control and terminate the immune response by the secretion of cytokines. As a defensive response to immediate threats such as infection or injury, the innate immune system initiates acute inflammation, whose cardinal signs include redness, pain, heat, and swelling (Kuprash and Nedospasov, 2016).

Challenges and solutions

There are numerous challenges faced in the provision of mental health screening and treatment for those in need, particularly within resource-constrained settings where HIV is endemic and the availability of mental health professionals and services is rare. Some models offer promising approaches to efficient and effective mental healthcare delivery especially in settings that have limited resources. These models are, stepped care, trans-diagnostic approaches, task shifting, and technology.

Stepped care

Stepped care offers patients the least intensive intervention required for their mental health needs, with advancements to more intensive treatments as necessary. Stepped care approaches find efficiency by triaging intervention intensity based upon observed need. Patients who do not benefit from initial, lower intensity interventions graduate to higher intensity or more resource-intensive interventions. Stepped care approaches have been used by several HIV-related mental health projects in sub-Saharan Africa. For example, a project in Zimbabwe piloted a stepped-care and task-shifted intervention for HIV patients with depression and low antiretroviral adherence (Abas et al, 2018). Currently, the concept of stepped care is widely adopted. The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence recommends a stepped care approach to primary health care for depression, generalised anxiety disorder, panic disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), obsessive–compulsive disorder, and body dysmorphic disorder.

Lay community health workers were trained to deliver a first-level intervention to patients (six sessions of problem-solving cognitive behavioral therapy for depression and medication adherence). Patients who did not benefit from the first-level intervention were triaged to more intensive treatment (an assessment by a trained clinician for potential provision of antidepressants and/or further counseling). A small pilot trial found reduced depression and improved viral load suppression among intervention recipients compared with enhanced standard care (Abas et al, 2018).

Transdiagnostic approaches

Transdiagnostic approaches represent another route to advance delivery of HIV-related mental healthcare in resource-constrained settings. The transdiagnostic model focuses on shared mechanisms across mental health disorders, such as emotion dysregulation, cognitive biases, and avoidance. It offers advantages in efficiency, accessibility, and treating comorbidity. According to Sauer-Zavala et al, transdiagnostic approaches recognize that different mental disorders (e.g. depression, anxiety) frequently co-occur and may share-related symptoms, so uniform treatment strategies might be employed to effectively address multiple mental health problems (Sauer-Zavala et al, 2017). Applications of transdiagnostic approaches to HIV include cognitive-behavioral counseling to concurrently address depression, anxiety, and HIV risk related to minority stress among young carriers.

Task shifting

Task shifting, an approach increasingly emphasized in global mental health care, holds promise for improving mental health care delivery. Task shifting involves the rational redistribution of tasks among health workforce teams. Specific tasks are moved, where appropriate, from highly qualified health workers to health workers with shorter training and fewer qualifications in order to make more efficient use of the available human resources for health. In the context of mental health screening and treatment, this represents a shift from mental health professionals to healthcare workers who lack formalized training in mental health.

Technology-based approaches

Technology-based approaches like telephone-delivered and computer-delivered interventions can help scale mental healthcare and support lay-counselor interventions with PLWH who are in need. According to Rosso et al, internet-based mental health interventions, such as internet-based cognitive behavioral therapies are growing in popularity globally to improve access in low resource contexts, as well as

among youth and young adults who are at high risk for nonadherence or nonaccess of mental health resources (Rosso et al, 2017).

Conclusion

The stigma of HIV can lead to significant psychological and psychosocial distress. As such, community and public health campaigns to reduce stigma may have a substantive mental health effect if properly relayed. Improved access to and understanding of HIV treatment and prevention could particularly reduce HIV stigma and benefit mental health.

Increased availability and use of effective HIV primary prevention tools could importantly benefit mental health, as well. The high efficacy of PrEP in nearly eliminating the risk of HIV acquisition among HIV-negative individuals adhering to PrEP has been shown to significantly reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression among young people vulnerable to acquiring HIV (Marcus et al, 2018).

At the end of this review, the following understanding about the convergence of mental health and HIV/AIDS

1. Mental health problems (ranging from distress to SMI) are high among people at-risk for HIV and PLWH. This risk is higher across populations most affected by the epidemic in different regions of the world.
2. Mental health problems contribute to HIV acquisition and poor outcomes along the HIV treatment continuum.
3. HIV acquisition and the resulting chronic immune activation increase the risk to develop mental health problems in most PLWH.
4. There are necessary screening and support tools available and treatments that are efficient to treat mental health problems among people living with and at risk for HIV.
5. Mental health treatment, need to be prioritize especially that which is integrated into HIV care, with appropriate resources to address the current screening and treatment gap.
6. Health policy makers could come up with community and public health driven campaigns relating to HIV treatment and prevention. This will help reduce stigma and psychological distress.
7. There have been great improvement in integrating mental healthcare into HIV primary care through various strategies viz, stepped-care interventions task shifting, among others.

Despite the many challenges that mental health presents to HIV prevention and treatment, there are many important unmet opportunities to integrate mental healthcare with HIV care. Initiatives like PEPFAR have helped countries around the world dramatically expand HIV care, and the concomitant strengthening of their healthcare systems has offered substantial benefits to wider healthcare delivery. Further integration of mental health screening and care into this infrastructure would not only strengthen HIV prevention and care outcomes, but it would additionally improve global access to mental healthcare.

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